

Original Research Article

Is Pilonidal disease variant of Hidradenitis Suppurativa? Study in a peripheral general hospital

^{*1}Prof. Saadeldin Ahmed Idris, ²Dr. Abdul Ghani Qureshi, ³Dr. Fauwaz Fahad Alrashid,
⁴Dr. Nahid Mubarak Ali and ⁵Dr. Hamid Elhadi Mohammed

Abstract

¹Department of Surgery, College of Medicine, University of Hail, KSA.

²Department of Surgery, Almikhwah General Hospital, Al-Baha, KSA

³Department of Surgery, College of Medicine, University of Hail, KSA

⁴Department of Dermatology, Almikhwah General Hospital, Al-Baha, KSA

⁵Department of Surgery, Almikhwah General Hospital, Al-Baha, KSA

*Corresponding Author's E-mail:
saadeldinahmed@hotmail.com

Pilonidal disease and hidradenitis suppurativa are chronic inflammatory diseases that affect young patients and can have a serious impact on their quality of life. The association between them was frequently reported but not well documented. This study aimed to determine the prevalence and characteristics of inflammatory skin lesions located in the intergluteal fold and axillae of patients with hidradenitis suppurativa and those with pilonidal disease. In retrospective manner the study based on data collection from records of a cohort of patients with hidradenitis suppurativa without histopathology and patients with pilonidal diseases with or without histopathology who had been managed in Almikhwah General Hospital, KSA during the period from January 2014 to April 2020. A total of 391 patients were recruited, 224(57.3%) with pilonidal diseases (Group A) and 167 (42.7%) with hidradenitis suppurativa diseases (Group B). Their mean age was 27.5 years (p=0.3). In group A, the lesions were found in sacrococcygeal region whereas in group B, it was found in axillae and sacrococcygeal region. Coincidences of the diseases were observed in 79 (20.2%) patients. In conclusion, it should be borne in mind that the pilonidal sinus can be a non-localized type of hidradenitis suppurativa.

Keywords: Pilonidal sinus disease (PSD), hidradenitis suppurativa (HS), hair follicle, follicular occlusion tetrad

INTRODUCTION

Pilonidal disease is an acquired chronic inflammatory disease of the skin and subcutaneous tissue in the sacrococcygeal region (Ekici et al., 2019; Young, 2019). It has a fluctuating trajectory for many years, which includes healing with episodes of acute flare-ups. Nevertheless, it is a self-limiting disease that disappears with age (Young, 2019).

The exact aetiology is unclear, although old theories hypothesize that the pilonidal sinus is congenital, but currently is considered an acquired disease (Ekici et al., 2019). Although various theories have been put forward since it was first described, no consensus has been

reached. Anderson was the first one to describe the pilonidal sinus disease (PSD) as a fistula in the hair bearing area close to the patient's coccyx. In 1854, Warren developed the description of PSD in more detail, provided guidelines for treatment, and proposed the first hypothesis for its development as a typical hair growth from superficial to deep and not from normal deep to superficial in the intergluteal cleft (Konoplitskyi et al., 2019).

From Fere (1878) to Stone (1951), several authors had put forward four different theories: the theory of the medullary canal, the theory of dermal inclusion, the

theory of the beak glands and the theory of the sex glands. All of these theories never been proven and not explained pilonidal disorders in places other than the sacrococcygeal region (Duman, Kazim et al., 2016).

In 1880 Hodges described PSD as an independent disease and gave a name with the Latin words "pillus" - hair and "nidus" - nest (Duman, Kazim et al., 2016; Stone, 1931). Since then, there have been multitude of medical terms that describe the same pathological process: coccyx epithelium passage, pilonidal cyst, sinus, extra dermal sacrococcygeal sinus cavity, sacral epithelial cleft/indentation, epithelial coccyx fistula/cyst, sacral funnel, posterior umbilicus, sequestral dermoid, and dermoid (Duman, Kazim et al., 2016; Smíd et al., 2011).

Hidradenitis suppurativa (HS), also known as acne inversa or Verneuil's disease, is a chronic debilitating and recurrent inflammatory disease, usually affects areas of the skin contain pilosebaceous glands (Smith et al., 2019). Mainly affects the armpits, groin and anogenital region (Alikhan et al., 2009; Fimmel et al., 2010).

It was first described in 1839 and received its name in 1854, during this period it was related to sweat glands (Fimmel et al., 2010; Velpeau, 2012; Verneuil, 1854; Pillsbury et al., 1956). It was then classified as a member of the triad of follicular occlusion with acne conglobata and dissecting cellulitis of the scalp (Pillsbury et al., 1956). At a later date, 1975, Pilonidal disease was added as a member of this triad, which formed the tetrad of follicular occlusion (Zouboulis et al., 2015; Wortsman et al., 2017). Finally, Plewig and Steger introduced the term acne inversa in 1989 to replace the term HS. However, the two terms HS and acne inversa are not proper denominations for the disease and do not represent their pathogenic background (Fimmel et al., 2010).

The exact aetiology of HS is still unproven. In the last few years, numerous studies hypothesized that the disease is triggered by genetic and environmental factors (Napolitano et al., 2017). The main defect in the pathophysiology of HS is the occlusion and subsequent inflammation of the hair follicle; these conditions in association with innate and adaptive deregulation of the immune system are necessary to initiate the development of clinical hidradenitis suppurativa disease (HSD) (Prens et al., 2015).

Bacterial infection and colonization are considered a secondary pathogenic factor that can worsen HS. Follicular occlusion results in dilation followed by rupture, which results in follicle content including keratin and bacteria that spills into the surrounding dermis and induces a violent chemotactic response from neutrophils and lymphocytes.

The infiltrate of inflammatory cells leads to the formation of abscesses, which leads to the destruction of the pilosebaceous unit and ultimately the other adjacent adnexal structures (Zouboulis et al., 2015; Napolitano et al., 2017; Kurzen, H, et al., 2008; Plewig et al., 1975). Its management is often shared between dermatology and

various surgical specialties (Collier et al., 2013). Li K and colleagues in 2011, concluded that pilonidal disease can be observed in HSD, but is generally found in the coccyx.

Hidradenitis suppurativa and pilonidal cysts often occur in areas where skin folds can be exposed to strong mechanical loads. Due to their location and the chronic nature of these lesions, the quality of life could be seriously affected (Boer et al., 2016).

The relationship between hidradenitis suppurativa and pilonidal sinus disease is still under investigation and debate as to whether there is a connection between different conditions or forms of the same disease. As claimed largely in the literature regarding the data in patients with hidradenitis suppurativa, there is a high prevalence of pilonidal sinus diseases which indicates a strong relation between the two disorders. Furthermore, it is believed that inflammation of the pilonidal sinus leads to the formation of a pilonidal cyst that has ultrasound-morphological properties similar to hidradenitis suppurativa (Temelkova et al., 2019).

The large number of terms used to describe the entity of these diseases throughout history reflects the considerable amount of researches carried out in this scope. This can lead to confusion and difficulty in understanding their pathology, finding definitive literary sources, and difficulty in evaluating the mentioned sources. This study aimed to determine the relationship between HS and PSD and to determine whether HS is the origin of the disease and PSD is a part or branch of HS.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

The patients in this study were retrospectively recruited from patients who were treated in the departments of general surgery and dermatology in AlMikhwah General Hospital in Al-Baha southern region of KSA (MGH) during the period from January 2014 to April 2020. Patients were grouped into group A (PSD group) including patients with pilonidal sinus (PS) and pilonidal abscess (PA), and group B (HSD) including patients with non-complicated hidradenitis suppurativa (HS) and patients with complicated (HA) as abscess. Sociodemographic, clinical, and data concerned with diagnosis, treatment, therapeutic responses, recurrence, patient's satisfaction and overall survival were gathered from patients' hospital records. Hand-written records were retrieved and reviewed for study population during study period. Each patient was included in the study once, even if was admitted more than once.

Accordingly, a patient diagnosed as non-complicated HS and transformed to abscess during follow-up was included in group of patients with abscess. Those who first presented to our hospital as PS and then developed abscess were included in group of patients with PA. Data was collected using a predesigned questionnaire, then

Table 1. Characteristics of the whole study population (n=391)

N	391 patients
Male	218 (55.75%)
Female	173 (44.25%)
Male: Female ratio	1.26: 1
PSD	224 (57.3%)
HSD	167 (42.7%)
Coincidences	79 (20.2%)
Age (year)	Mean 27.5±9.7 (range, 16 to 65), p=0.3
Duration of symptoms days	Mean 39.4± 48.9 (range, 2 to 180), p=0.0001
Duration of antibiotics (days)	Mean 11.5± 10.4 (range, 1 to 28), p=0.0001
Duration of analgesics (days)	Mean 3.3± 0.4 (range, 2 to 5), p=0.001
Hospital stay (days)	Mean. 1.4± 1.1 (range, 0 to 4), p=0.0001

Table 2. Characteristics of the patients with pilonidal diseases, Group A(PSD) (n=224)

N	224 patients
Male	155 (63.5%)
Female	69 (36.5%)
Male: Female ratio	2.25: 1
PS	181 (80.8%)
PA	43 (19.2%)
Age (year)	Mean 23.83± 4.9 (range, 16 to 38) p=0.3
Duration of symptoms (days)	Mean 65.8± 50.7 (range, 5 to 180) p=0.001
Duration of antibiotics (days)	Mean 4.9± 3.1 (range, 1 to 11) p=0.14
Duration of analgesics (days)	Mean 3.6± 0.65 (range, 3 to 5) p=0.8
Hospital stay (days)	Mean 2.1 ± 0.83 (range, 1 to 4) p=0.002
Recurrence	PS 4/181 (2.2%), PA 12/43 (27.9%) p=0.00001

distributed in master sheet and entered into the computer system. Analysis of the collected data was done with SPSS software, version 21 (SPSS Inc., Chicago). Descriptive data were shown as mean and standard deviation (SD) if it is quantitative or as percentages for qualitative variables. The chi-square test was used to estimate association between categorical variables. *P* value <0.05 was considered significant. The study was in line with the Helsinki Declaration on Medical Research. Furthermore, the study protocol was approved by hospital administration before handling patients' records. However, patients' written informed consents to review their medical records was not required, as that would be inappropriate due to the retrospective nature of the study, where a considerable proportion of patients stopped follow-up, or were living in distant governorates. Confidentiality was ensured by processing patient records, replacing patient names with search codes and entering data into a personal computer.

RESULTS

Demography

Of the 320313 records of new cases registered in MGH during the study period, a total of 391 patients were

identified to have the diagnosis of either HSD or PSD. This led to an incidence rate of 0.0122 per 100,000 clinic population. Two hundred and eighteen (55.75%) males and 173 (44.25%) were females with a ratio of 1.7:1. Their age ranged from 16 to 65 with a mean of 27.52 ±9.7 years (*P*=0.3). There were 224 (57.3%) patients with pilonidal disease (Group A) and 167 (42.7%) had hidradenitis suppurativa disease (Group B). Coincidences with HS were found in 79 (20.2%). There was significant difference in the duration of illness before being diagnosed with the disease, as patients with HSD being present earlier (*p* = 0.0001). General patients' characteristics were shown in Table 1.

Group A (PSD)

Table 2 shows the characteristics of the patients presented with PSD. Two hundred and twenty-four patients (male: 155, female: 69) were diagnosed with PSD. One hundred and eighty-one (80.8%) had PS and the remainder 43 (19.2%) had PA that was treated surgically. In PS, surgical modality was fashioned according to the extent of the disease and the number of sinus openings (Figure 1), whereas, all PAs were managed by incision and drainage (Figure 2).

There was no significant difference concerning

Figure 1. Number of sinus openings in patients with PSD in group A (n=224)

Figure 2. Surgical management of patients with PSD (n=224)

duration of postoperative pain control, antibiotics usage, patient's satisfaction and recurrence rate ($p > 0.05$). However, we determined that the patients with PS managed by primary repair (simple closure and Limberg flap) had recovery time significantly shorter compared to patients managed by secondary healing. Therefore, we recommended primary repair in the treatment of PS. Post-operative histopathology results came in favour of the primary diagnosis in all specimens.

Hospital stay was shorter in the group of patients with PA than with PS, the difference was statistically significant ($P=0.02$). Surgical site infection developed in 7 (3.9%) patients treated because of PS. Recurrence rate was 4/181 (2.2%) in patients with PS and 12/43 (27.9%) in patients with PA, the difference was significant ($p=0.00001$). Over all patients' satisfaction is shown in

Figure 3, it was of noteworthy as it was very good/excellent in 187(83.5%).

In group A 70/224 (31.25%) patients had coincide HS (PS; seen in 61, and PA; seen in 9), the difference was not significant ($p=0.1$).

Group B (HSD)

All patients in this group diagnosed on clinical base. Table 3 shows the characteristics of the patients presented with HSD. One hundred and sixty-seven patients (Female: 105, Male: 62) were diagnosed with HSD, with Male to Female ratio of 1:1.7. One hundred and thirteen (67.7%) had HS and the remainder 54 (32.3%) had HA.

Figure 3. Patients' satisfaction in group A (PSD) (n=224)

Table 3. Characteristics of the patients with hidradenitis suppurativa diseases, Group B (HSD) (n=167)

N	167 patients
Male	62 (37.1%)
Female	105 (62.9%)
Male: Female ratio	1: 1.7
HS	113 (67.7%)
HA	54 (32.3%)
Age (year)	Mean 32.4± 12.1 (range, 16 to 65) p=0.3
Duration of symptoms (days)	Mean 4.1± 1.5 (range, 2 to 7) p=0.003
Duration of antibiotics (days)	Mean 20.2± 10.3 (range, 7 to 28) p=0.000
Duration of analgesics (days)	Mean 2.9± 0.8 (range, 2 to 5) p=0.006
Hospital stay (days)	Mean 0.5 ± 0.7 (range, 0 to 2) p=0.000

Figure 4. Patients' satisfaction in group B (HSD) (n=167)

Patients with HS were treated with a protocol adopted in our hospital of extended 3 days oral azithromycin 500 mg every week for 4 weeks, topical fucidin 20 mg ointment/mupricin, plus oral diclofenac sodium 50 mg twice a day, for 3 to 5 days if not contraindicated.

All patients with HA were managed by incision and draining followed by antibiotics according to the result of

culture and sensitivity plus oral diclofenac sodium 50 mg if no contraindications.

There was significant difference concerning duration of symptoms, duration of postoperative pain control, antibiotics usage, hospital stay, and patient's satisfaction ($p < 0.05$).

Recurrence rate was observed in 24 (14.4%) patients

(HS 2/113 (1.8%), HA 22/54 (40.7%)), the difference was significant $p=00001$. Over all, patients' satisfaction in group B is shown in Figure 4. It was of noteworthy as it was very good/excellent in 139 (83.2%).

DISCUSSION

Pilonidal cysts and hidradenitis suppurativa are related inflammatory conditions that have been included in "follicular occlusion tetrad" because of sharing a plugging of the hair follicles in their pathophysiological mechanisms (Wortsman et al., 2017).

The current study found that the incidence of PSD is more common than HSD, as seen in 57.3% and 42.7% respectively. This finding was in agreement with Vasanth and colleagues (2014) who mentioned that PSD is much more common than HSD.

PSD was more frequent in young men whereas HSD group was mainly composed of young women. This was in consistence with the report done by Wortsman et al., 2017; Konoplitskyi et al., 2019.

Both diseases found predominantly affecting the young people as their mean age was 27.5 years. Similar findings were obtained by others (Alikhan et al., 2009; Fimmel et al., 2010; Li et al., 2011; Wortsman et al., 2017; Pesce et al., 2018; Konoplitskyi et al., 2019; Young, 2019).

Pilonidal disease may be observed in as much as one-third of patients with hidradenitis suppurativa (HS) (Pesce et al., 2018). In this study, coincidence of HSD and PSD was observed in 20.2%.

In the current study, the diagnosis of HSD and PSD was made on clinical base not necessitated by histopathology. This method was governed in literature where the diagnosis of HS as well as PSD is usually made on clinical grounds and biopsies with histopathology are not routinely taken (Rongioletti, 2017) because of its usually large extent and multizone type of involvement (von Laffert et al., 2011; Wortsman et al., 2017). No specific laboratory studies or tests are needed for diagnosis or to differentiate them from other disease entities (Vasanth et al., 2014). For this reason, only a few studies are dealing with histopathological features (Rongioletti, 2017). So far, pilonidal cysts and hidradenitis suppurativa have been considered and treated as separate entities. For example, pilonidal cysts tend to be surgically treated, and hidradenitis suppurativa cases are medically managed by dermatologist in the early or intermediate stages of severity (Wortsman et al., 2017).

A closer link between pilonidal cysts and hidradenitis suppurativa has been suggested by von Laffert M et al. (2011) as they observed a similar histological feature of pilonidal cysts to those reported in hidradenitis suppurativa that let them to propose that PSD could be a unilocalized type of HS, and both present with alterations of the hair.

CONCLUSION

PSD and HSD diseases are chronic, debilitating conditions of young adults. Individuals can suffer either or both. Therefore, prompt treatment is required to reduce and limit disease burden. Despite the extensive research in this era, there still doesn't exist a universal consensus as to the etiology of PSD and HSD and their definitive pathogenesis. The two groups of disorders are possibly having the same disease process. The high prevalence of PSD indicates a strong relation between PSD and HSD. Thus, it can be profitable to recognize common pathophysiological mechanisms and evolve common therapeutic master plan. Pilonidal sinus disease was not distinctly disclosed in patients with hidradenitis suppurativa. This is the first study to examine the prevalence of pilonidal sinus disease in a large patient in a single periphery hospital and identify patient characteristics and their satisfaction regarding the treatment strategies. Treatment should be personalized according to the clinical portray. The clinical outcome may be related to the level of interest doctors have in the subject and their knowledge. The current study underlines the importance of close collaboration between general surgeons and dermatologists under interwoven clinical conditions.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this article.

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